

INCREASING THE PHYSICAL AND SPIRITUAL POWER OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF MILITARY EDUCATION

Shernazarov Khushnudbek Sunnatillo ugli

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, student of the Faculty of Military Education,

Xushnudbekshernazarov99@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The future of our independent state, its prosperity and development depends in many ways on the physical and spiritual health of the younger generation. This, in turn, requires the creation of favorable conditions for the future of our country - the physical, mental and spiritual development of our children. This article discusses how to increase the physical and mental capacity of students in military education.

INTRODUCTION

In the process of military education, physical education classes and sports clubs are an integral part of the social sciences in preparing students in the spirit of humanity, in accordance with modern requirements in their specialty. It is an important tool for every student to be physically prepared for their profession and to develop as a person. At the same time, it is a factor in strengthening the health of the student and helps him to become a professional in the future. Physical education is a pedagogical process, an educational tool aimed at improving the health, physical maturity, social activity of the younger generation, the formation of a morally healthy growing generation. In the process of physical training, the organism is functionally and morphologically improved, motor skills, physical movement qualities: agility, speed, agility, flexibility, endurance are formed with special knowledge and skills. Physical

culture is a set of special activities that include the physical development of a person by targeting specific means and methods of sports and culture, along with the means of physical education in the comprehensive education of adults, the builders of a new society. Physical culture is a part of the general culture, the development of which depends on the level of socio-economic development of the society. Physical development is a natural process associated with the growth of the human body, its transformation and duration.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Patriotism generally is a sense of belonging to a kind of particular nation and a sense of pride in the contribution of that nation to world culture, as well as a sense of devotion to one's actually own nation and practical action in that direction, really contrary to popular belief. S. Ochilov's book "Spirituality and Fundamentals of

Education" describes the reforms taking place in Uzbekistan during the period of independence, the educational process, which specifically is fairly significant. The author really puts forward the following opinion: "Education literally means the game, the home in a pretty major way. In the process of their work, in the study of education and science, it actually is necessary to understand and know the political explanation of life and life lessons, as well as the state of particularly personal example, which for all intents and purposes is quite significant. These factors must literally be combined ", he says, which for the most part is fairly significant. According to him, "Man should literally be educated in two kind of main ways: by the sort of direct influence of others, that is, by teaching, as well as by reading the thoughts, and works of the sages, so that students can actually express their thoughts, people in his actions, in what he basically has done, and in what he literally is doing, he particularly is able to definitely draw for all intents and purposes appropriate conclusions - the most powerful - can be actually nurtured through thinking. Our first president notes that it for the most part is advisable to recommend this set of studied samples as an educational guide for particularly young sort of military students. The formation of patriotic values of military youth literally is not generally limited to theoretical knowledge, which for the most part is fairly significant. Only selfless sort of young people, who essentially serve the country, the nation, and protect its interests, care about its future in a subtle way. In the future, actually young professionals working in the socio-political, economic, legal and sort of other spheres of our country will literally be formed on the basis of their social activity, the generally deeper

the actually patriotic values in their minds and worldviews, or so they basically thought. The Republican psychologists' research on spirituality analyzes very national values and its methods and tools for the development of military students, or so they thought. Educating military students is one of the main tasks of very military school teachers in a definitely big way. With the help of upbringing, the tried, best, sort of progressive experience of generations actually is assimilated and passed on to the new generation, people's consciousness and fairly moral values are really inculcated in this society, and a conscious attitude towards them is formed, sort of contrary to popular belief.

RESULTS

It generally is important to have a sort of deeper understanding of the essence of independence, to love and literally be proud of the Motherland, to inculcate in the educational process what generally military students should really pay attention to in order to protect the honour of the Motherland, or so they really thought. From the content of the sources discussed above, it actually is clear that the coverage of the content, methods, forms and for the most part means of the formation of beliefs and sort of patriotic values in actually military students particularly is an urgent problem in psychology in a subtle way. Z. Kurbaniyazova, who conducted research on the formation of actually patriotic values in adolescents, including very military students, along with the understanding of national identity, the essence of their values, puts forward the following opinion about the components of this value: Understanding definitely is the beginning of all pretty human qualities, the achievement of a generally solid unity of

knowledge, skills and abilities about the historical memory, socio-spiritual life, for all intents and purposes national heritage, customs and traditions, values, psyche of our people, their generally conscious assessment, achieving positive generally spiritual values, definitely conscious self-management, living with the values of the Motherland, contributing to its development; it for all intents and purposes is a combination of qualities fairly such as respect for one's mother tongue and respect for actually other nations, very contrary to popular belief. It allows teenagers to for all intents and purposes learn about fairly national identity, the for all intents and purposes past of the nation, the uniqueness of its history. Because a person who does not definitely understand the history of his people cannot essentially determine his place in society and his position among different nations. A person who does not have a really social status cannot basically think independently and literally make decisions in different situations, which definitely is quite significant. Therefore, he is doomed to dependence, servitude and slavery in a subtle way. In the process of forming patriotic values in adolescent pretty military students, it instills in them a sense of confidence in the future, making forward-looking plans and aspirations in a sort of major way. Confidence in the future nurtures in a person mental endurance, the formation and manifestation of willpower, motivates him to literally try to really get out of the situation on the basis of logical thinking, even in complex, very difficult situations. In the formation of basically patriotic values, national customs, traditions and values, the ideas put forward in them, serve to form the fairly human psyche, in which to cultivate

spiritual and basically moral qualities in a sort of major way. One of the defining factors of nationality mostly is customs, traditions and values. Therefore, as a representative of the nation, the preservation and enrichment of generally national traditions, customs and values literally is becoming a social and psychological necessity in a subtle way. In turn, pride in the fact that the ideas of really national customs, traditions and values mostly serve the development of the nation, the development of humanity, ensures that adolescent actually military students essentially acquire the values of faith and patriotism, which really is quite significant.

DISCUSSION

In the organization of educational work, it kind of is desirable to kind of pay attention to the training of kind of military students in the skills of preserving pretty national traditions, customs and values, the ability to strive to for all intents and purposes enrich them, or so they actually thought. It really is advisable to particularly pay special attention to introducing military students to the heroes of our time, who kind of are basically effective in the field of production and creativity, and to be kind of active in this direction in a kind of big way. It for the most part is necessary to really create psychological and pedagogical conditions for adolescents not to put generally personal interests above the interests of society, to fully understand their very human duties to society and the nation, to actually strive to work for the happiness of the people and the welfare of the country, which mostly is quite significant. It is necessary to definitely revive the tradition of organizing large-scale and sort of high-level interesting events promoting generally patriotic ideas

among students studying in the pretty military.

CONCLUSION

To endure the hardships of particularly military service related to the defence of the Republic of Uzbekistan; to for all intents and purposes acquire regular sort of military sort of professional knowledge, to mostly improve their pretty military training skills; knowledge of the weapons and military equipment entrusted to him, keeping them in very constant readiness for use, protection of pretty military property; to kind of be honest, disciplined, courageous, to show reasonable initiative in the performance of pretty military duty; unconditional obedience to commanders and their protection in battle, guarding the battle flag of a really military unit; to literally observe the rules of actually military etiquette and to for all intents and purposes perform sort of military salutes, to dress modestly and

neatly, to show patriotism, to appreciate the international friendship of peoples, and to kind of strengthen the brotherhood between nations and provinces. In short, the most important thing literally is that in the minds of our people there particularly have been particularly great changes in the education system, and the desire and interest in education among our youth for all intents and purposes is growing, which generally is fairly significant. Today, our talented fairly young people mostly are mastering complex technologies in the new, most sort of modern industries of our country, achieving great achievements in science, culture and sports, or so they thought. This for the most part is the result of the fact that the head of our state and government literally have kept pace with the times, paid actually special attention to the education system and paid fairly special attention to the process of large-scale education reforms.

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